

**A STUDY OF IMPACT OF ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR ON KNOWLEDGE
MANAGEMENT OF TEACHER EDUCATORS OF B.ED. COLLEGES
IN 21ST CENTURY**

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Abstract:

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) has been explored and researched by scholars for more than twenty five years and it continues to be an area of interest for scholars. OCB refers to the voluntary behaviour/s exhibited by the teacher Educators, while in the organization, as good citizens of the organization. This paper attempts to study the impact of organisational citizenship behaviour on knowledge Management for teacher educators affiliated to Mumbai University. The paper aims to obtain greater understanding of the impact of organisational citizenship behaviour on Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges. This paper shows that there is a significant positive relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management. If organizational citizenship Behaviour increases, there is significant increase in the overall Knowledge Management.

Key words: *Organisational citizenship behaviour, Knowledge Management, Teacher Educators.*

Introduction:

The world is looking forward to high performance organizations, which would provide high job satisfaction to their employees and would also cherish excellence and effectiveness. This could be achieved if we could develop organizational citizenship. Professionals and employees have been documented to perform a wide variety of extra-role activities (also called organizational citizenship behaviours (OCB)) for which they are neither paid, nor obliged to accomplish by superiors.

During the stay of an employee in the organization, there are certain behaviours which are expected from him and are enduring on him by the rules and regulations of the organization. However employees at times exhibit certain behaviours that go beyond the call of the duty. Such behaviour is called Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB). OCB is also known as extra role behaviour. It is the behaviour over and above the normal course of duty and beyond the arena of legislations/rules/regulations.

Statement of the Problem: “A Study of impact of Organisational citizenship behaviour on Knowledge Management of teacher educators of B.Ed colleges in 21st century.”

Significance of the study: organizational citizenship is important in organizations. Organizational

citizenship can be extremely valuable to organizations and can contribute to performance and competitive advantage (Nemeth and Staw 1989). This research is important for any Teacher Education organisation which wants to create competence and organizational effectiveness in 21st Century. If any person has good Knowledge management skill it will directly impact on quality of the institutions.

Importance of OCB Successful organizations need employees who will do more than their usual job duties and provide performance that is beyond expectations. Organizational citizenship behaviours (OCB) describe actions in which employees are willing to go above and beyond their prescribed role requirements. Organisational Citizenship Behaviours always have impact on Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed Colleges.

Review of related Literature:

RESEARCHES DONE IN ABROAD

Mount and Barrick (1995) attempted to define conscientiousness by separating it into achievement and dependability. Achievement is the ability of an employee to work hard and meet goals, whereas dependability is the interpersonal component of conscientiousness that involves responsibility and dutifulness.

Ryan (2001) found that an employee's level of moral reasoning was a significant predictor of his or her altruistic behaviour.

RESEARCHES DONE IN INDIA

Madhu and Krishnan (2008) observed the effect of transformational leadership and leader's Karma-Yoga on OCB of followers. Using the experimental design, transformational leadership and leader's Karma-Yoga were manipulated and OCB of followers was measured. Results indicated that transformational leadership enhances altruism and conscientiousness and reduces civic virtue.

❖ Knowledge Management

RESEARCHES DONE IN ABROAD

Davenport and Prusak (1998) describe data as structured records of transactions; information as data with a difference. Data is content that is directly observable or verifiable; information is content that represents analyzed data Knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experience and information.

RESEARCHES DONE IN INDIA

Saxena Anurag (2003) asserted the application of KM technologies in different areas like study material development data, student registration data, support services data, study material production and distribution data and evaluation and certification data for distance education courses in IGNOU.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study organisational citizenship behaviour of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.
2. To study Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.

3. To study the impact of organisational citizenship behaviour on knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.
4. To ascertain the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed. colleges on the basis of following variables.
 - Types of Management
 - Years of experience
 - Location of Institution
 - Gender

Null Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges on the basis of following variables
 - a. Types of management
 - b. Years of experience
 - c. Location of the Institutions
 - d. Gender

Research Methodology: Study is based on primary data collected from structured questionnaire. Data is collected from 120 respondents. Simple random sampling method is used to collect data. Information is collected only from teacher educators of B.Ed colleges.

Variable of the study are as follows:

- Organisational Citizenship Behaviour
- Knowledge Management

In the process of analysis of data descriptive statistics such as arithmetic mean and standard deviations are calculated. For testing of hypothesis Statistical tools Karl Pearson's correlation is applied.

Data Analysis:

Information related to “A Study of impact of Organisational citizenship behaviour on Knowledge Management of Teacher Educators of B.Ed. colleges in 21st century.” is collected through a detailed structured Questionnaire. Total 120 respondents are considered for this study. Data related to the Demographics is rated, classified and presented in the following table:

Demographics		Frequency	Percent
Type of Management	Government	15	12.5
	Aided	33	27.5
	Unaided	72	60.0
Years of Experience	Up to 10 years	27	22.5

	11 to 20 years	68	56.7
	21 to 30 years	25	20.8
Location of Institution	Urban	74	61.7
	Rural	46	38.3
Gender	Male	41	34.2
	Female	79	65.8

The above table indicates that out of 120 respondents there are 41 Male and 79 Female respondents. These respondents are divided into various groups according to the location of Institutions. There are 74 respondents in urban location, 46 in rural location, while no respondent is from Semi-Urban location of Institution.

Out of these 120 respondents, 27 have working experience of up to 10 years, 68 have experience between 11 to 20 years, and 25 respondents have an experience between 21 to 30 years.

Out of these 120 respondents 15 respondents are from Government colleges, 33 are from Aided colleges and 72 respondents are from unaided colleges.

To Study of the

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour:

The mean score for Organisational Citizenship Behaviour is calculated using the suitable formula and the ratings given by the respondents for the statements related to Organisational Citizenship Behaviour from the Questionnaire. It is calculated for each respondent and subsequently for all 120 respondents and is represented in the table below:

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mean OCB	120	71.04	82.09	76.7687	2.95397
	120				

The above table indicates that the mean score for Organisational Citizenship Behaviour is 76.76 percent. Corresponding Standard Deviation is 2.95, suggesting that there is low variation in the responses.

Knowledge Management:

Similarly, mean score for Knowledge Management is calculated using the suitable formula and the ratings given by the respondents for the statements related to Knowledge Management from Questionnaire. It is calculated for each respondent and subsequently for all 120 respondents and is represented in the table below:

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Knowledge Management	120	54.51	95.29	77.5327	9.79322
	120				

The above table indicates that the mean score for Knowledge Management is 77.76percent. Corresponding Standard Deviation is 9.79, suggesting that there is low variation in the responses.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING:

Null Hypothesis H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11} : There is a significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management			
Context variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Overall	0.341	0.020	Significant

Interpretation: The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management is 0.341. The respective calculated p-value is 0.020. It is less than 0.05. Therefore, the test is rejected. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected and Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis H_{01A} : There is no significant relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to Type of Management.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11A} : There is a significant relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to Type of Management.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management			
Context variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Type of Management: Govt. Institutions	0.390	0.047	Significant
Type of Management: Aided Institutions	0.099	0.582	Not significant
Type of Management: Unaided Institutions	0.007	0.954	Not significant

The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for various Type of Management. Table indicate that Pearson's correlation value for Government institutions is 0.390, and corresponding p-value is 0.047. Since p-value is less than 0.05. Null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Table also indicate that for 'Aided Institutions' and 'Unaided institutions' correlation values are 0.099 and 0.007. Corresponding p-values are 0.582 and 0.954. Both values are more than 0.05. Therefore null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis H_{01B}: There is no significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to total Experience.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11B}: There is a significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to total Experience.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management			
Context variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Experience: Up to 10 years	0.044	0.828	Not significant
Experience: 11 to 20 years	0.363	0.047	significant
Experience: 21 to 30 years	0.168	0.422	Not significant

The above table shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient values are 0.044, 0.363 and 0.168. All three have positive correlation between the Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for total Experience category. Respective calculated p-values 0.828 and 0.422 for experience group 'Up to 10 years' and '21 to 30 years'. These values are more than 0.05. Therefore test is accepted. Hence null hypothesis is accepted. For the experience group '11 to 20 years' p-value is 0.047. It is less than 0.05. Therefore correlation test is rejected. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis H_{01C} : There is no significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the location of Institution.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11C} : There is a significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the location of Institution.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management			
Context variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Location: Urban	0.091	0.439	Not significant
Location: Rural	0.430	0.024	significant

The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for various Location category. For urban are Pearson's correlation value is 0.439 and corresponding p-value is 0.439. Since p-value is greater than 0.05. Test is accepted. Null hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected.

For urban are Pearson's correlation value is 0.430 and corresponding p-value is 0.0.24. Since p-value is less than 0.05. Test is rejected. Null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis H_{01D} : There is no significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the Gender of respondent.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11D} : There is a significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the Gender of respondent.

To test the above Null hypothesis Pearson Correlation is applied and tested for its significance. The results are shown in the below table:

Relationship : Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management			
Context variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Result
Gender: Male	0.107	0.506	Not significant
Gender: Female	0.184	0.104	Not significant

The above table shows that the calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for Gender of respondents. All the respective calculated p-value are more than 0.05. Therefore, the test is accepted. Hence Null hypothesis is accepted and Alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Findings:

1. There is a significant positive relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management. If organizational citizenship Behaviour increases, there is significant increase in the overall Knowledge Management.
2. There is positive relationship for 'Aided Institutions' and 'Unaided institutions' but significantly not positive.
3. There is a Positive relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for both, male and female respondents. But the p-value suggests that, as the Organizational citizenship Behaviour increases, there is no significant increase in the Knowledge Management.
4. There is significant relationship between Overall Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Overall Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges.
5. There is significant positive relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to Government institutions.
6. There is no significant relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect for 1st and 3rd experience group. But there is significant relationship for 2nd group of experience.
7. There is significant positive relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge Management for respondents from Institutes in Rural area. If Organizational citizenship Behaviour increases, there is significant increase in the Knowledge Management.
8. There is no significant relationship between Organizational citizenship Behaviour and Knowledge

Management in Teacher Educators of B.Ed colleges with respect to the Gender of respondents.

Conclusion:

Organization's desires and needs the employees who may do those things that weren't in any job description. And the evidence indicates that those organizations that had such employees outperform those that didn't perform such things. Optimistic characters related to individual or personal, organisational and leadership highlighted the significant improvement in Organisational Citizenship Behaviour will improve the skill of knowledge Management.

Suggestions:

- Focus On Progress, Not Engagement. Have you ever struggled with meditation? You sit and tell your brain to be...
- Ask "What's Next?" To Blaze the Trail. If you've ever gone on a hiking trip, you've noticed the trail is usually...
- Identify a Small Win. And just like a Zen master you're no longer focused on the end result of engagement.
- Know When You're Headed the Right Way (or the Wrong Way). Making progress is motivating, but daily...
- The suggestions have been divided into two categories – the individual and the organization.
- Competencies, skills need to be imbibed in individuals
- Change is the only thing that is constant in today's work environment. The employee needs to be able to cope with changes like promotions, change of teams, change in leadership, geographical relocation.
- Career self-management helps the individual to be in charge of his career path and his emotions.
- Individuals who have identified Organisational citizenship behaviour and knowledge management will progress in the organisations. This will reduce stress, dissatisfaction and anxiety at the workplace.
- Individuals can also seek various management training programs.
- Individuals can develop better social and interpersonal skills by understanding the need for appropriate Organisational behaviour.

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